

Management

MADRASAH TRANSFORMATION MODEL OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ERA

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Abstract

Madrasah organizational transformation in the information technology era is not always successful, there are important things that must be considered by organizations, namely: the possibility of rejection of the transformation. Organizational transformation done by reengineering, for example, has a risk of failure caused by resistance to changes in the status quo. That is, if the organization can reduce the risk of resistance to organizational transformation, the organizational transformation will be successful.

In addition, to succeed in organizational transformation, support and involvement of top management is needed, a clear vision of change, a model of change especially for Human Resources is planned carefully, involving all parties at various levels of management in planning and implementing organizational transformation, employees must also be more empowered.

Keywords: Madrasah Transformation; Information Technology.

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1. Introduction

The development of science and technology has brought transformation in almost all aspects of human life where various problems cannot be solved except through the mastery and improvement of science and technology. The modern world especially in the era of globalization is a world that is familiar with transformation.

Globalization demands more rapid transformation in all lines of life. Today's global transformation is largely due to information and communication technology (ICT) factors. The development of ICT has brought extraordinary transformation, both in the social, economic, political, cultural, and others. The organization as a system must continue to adapt, transform, and carry out transformations in a better direction so that the movement and pace of the organization can be dynamic and sustainable.

Transformation as said by many circles is something that is eternal. Transformation is also an important part of management. Transformation is also an indicator of the success and ability of a leader in predicting and making it an opportunity. The main purpose of transformation is to improve the organization and make it more effective, although increasing organizational effectiveness is not easy. Organizational effectiveness explains the smooth running of departments and organizational operations such as the absence of conflict, turnover, and absenteeism.

Renewal is a necessity and necessity in the world of education, both formal and non-formal education. Advances in science and technology require humans to continue to race in exploring science. Allah SWT said:

Meaning: "O congregation of jinn and humans, if you are able to penetrate (cross) the corners of heaven and earth, then cross it, you cannot penetrate it except by force". (Surat Ar-Rahman: 33)

Therefore, improving the quality of human resources is a reality that must be carried out in a planned, directed, intensive, effective and efficient manner in the development process, otherwise the nation is unable to compete in undergoing the era of globalization. Globalization occurs, among others, due to the progress of science and technology, especially information technology, which is increasingly growing rapidly; so according to the fundamental transformation in various fields of life, economy, politics, social, and culture, including education.

The transformation is a common phenomenon that occurs throughout time in every social order, the transformation also occurs in accordance with the nature and nature of human beings who always want to change from one state to another for the better. Pudjiwati Sajagyo quoted Hirschman's opinion as saying that human boredom is the cause of transformation.

2. Discussion

2.1. Madrasah Transformation

Transformation is the movement or dynamics of a certain stage, both evolutionary and revolutionary, on a local or global scale that occurs due to internal or external factors. Transformation means transforming, varying, or modifying existing ways of thinking or behaving. In organizations, transformation is an important impetus and a major product of the organization's efforts, reshaping the way people and groups work together. Transformation in organizations is pervasive, which means that it is a normal part and needs to be organized. Whenever managers try to transform their movements, however, they should expect resistance, because people tend to reject what they perceive as a threat to those who do something the more drastic the transformation, the stronger the resistance that may result.

Organizational transformation is a move towards a better way to maintain the organization's existence against the demands of the transformation of the times. Organizations are always changing because nothing is eternal in this world, everything is changing, including the organization; what doesn't change is transformation itself. Transformation between organizational change (organizational change) with organizational development (organizational development) is an organizational transformation focusing on individuals, interactions between individuals within

the organization, and the organization itself. While organizational development is a transformation to increase the value and presence of organizational resources, such as training managers in improving their competence in problem solving, training organizational members as their subordinates.

A transformation is an effort that must be done by the individual himself. This is because a change in one's destiny is largely determined by the individual or the people themselves. The Word of Allah SWT:

Meaning: That (torment) is because surely Allah will never change something that He has bestowed upon a people, until that people change what is in themselves.

The Prophet also made a transformation in his life, this can be seen from the hadith below:

Meaning: Ibn Abbas, related that Rasûl SAW received a revelation when he was forty years old, then remained in Mecca for thirteen years, then was ordered to migrate. He moved to Medina and was there for ten years until he died. (Muslim HR).

The above hadith explains that the Messenger of Allah was ordered to emigrate to develop Islamic da'wah to be more advanced and developed. Likewise, all Muslims are also ordered to emigrate or transform to move forward.

2.2. Transformation in Islam

The meaning of transformation in Islam is known as the word tajdid. Besides the word tajdid, Rahman in Ali Sibram introduced the word islah as the meaning of change. Both tajdid and islah are efforts to realize social institutions in accordance with the goals that are aspired. The transformation movement in Islam can simply be interpreted as an individual or collective effort at a certain time and situation to make changes to the perception and practice of Islam. Islam does not reject the existence of transformation, even Islam actualizes the transformation from the beginning of its presence and the existence of mujaddid which alternates from century to century which does transformation in all areas of life and involves all needs in society.

Discussed in the context of leadership, the transformation brought by the Prophet Muhammad SAW was when the Prophet s.a.w succeeded in changing the civilization of the jahiliyyah era at that time. Based on research sirah, before the Prophet Muhammad was appointed apostle, moral conditions at that time were low such as free gambling activities, adultery, seizing property, cruel killings and oppression for the weak. But this situation changed when the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) became an apostle and as a result of the transformation leadership brought by the Prophet Muhammad, the social life of the people became better and more prosperous.

This change will not occur if the Prophet Muhammad did not apply the characteristics of a good leader and have leadership principles that must be emulated. The principles such as intention, piety, gratitude, shura and trust are what bring changes in the leadership of the Prophet Muhammad to the leadership style of transformation. The authority of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) is also a high ideal influence to allow His Majesty to influence his followers in carrying out capable,

sensitive and concerned management of the needs of the Ummah, having accurate goals and having clear insight. The concept of qudwah hasanah which is highlighted by Rasulullah s.a.w should be emulated by all Muslims and needs to be applied in a leader either male or female and the leader of a family, organization or country.

Religion in the function of transformation, which is to move the dynamics of religious teachings into a creative work that is always contextual with the reality in which religion exists so that religion does not lose its meaning in different dimensions. In addition, religious teachings are also absolutely transformed in the joints of human life so that religion is not always far from reality and is not affordable by human understanding. Religion is revealed to humans, so their understanding must be human and the practice must be transformed humanely as well. Islam came to change society towards a better quality of life, as reflected by the high level of obedience to God, knowledge of the Shari'a, and the release of the people from the burden of poverty, ignorance and so on, as well as various kinds of fetters which clamped down on human freedom.

Strong character is very important to have in human life and life, because character is not only a focal point that reflects the character of the nation's children, but also a process of finding the character of the nation and becomes the main axis behind the success of the development of national civilization. Towards the creation of social piety as an effort to create a society based on the value of equality and justice as well as an effort to create the benefit of the people. Globalization needs to be recognized and understood and responded to appropriately. This phenomenon has changed many facets of the life of the world community, and globalization is not just a perception of the flow of information in the extreme because of the advancement of communication technology. In the global world, the fields above are intertwined broadly, closely and in a fast process. This relationship is marked by the relationship between the inhabitants of the earth that goes beyond conventional conventions, such as the boundary between nation and the State.

2.3. Organizational Transformation in the Information Technology Era

Organizational transformation is transformation is a shift from the present state of an organization to the desired state in the future. The transformation can occur in organizational structure, work mechanism processes, human resources, and culture. The purpose of transformation is to improve the organization to adapt to the transformation of the environment and on the other hand to strive to transform employee behavior. Environmental transformation can be an external or internal environment of an organization. If it is associated with management, transformation management is a process of managing all elements associated with transformation to achieve organizational goals, both intentional transformation and self-generated transformation.

Transformation itself is a process in which we move from the prevailing conditions to the desired conditions carried out by individuals, groups and organizations in terms of reacting to internal and external dynamic forces. Organizational transformation is a move towards a better way to maintain the organization's existence against the demands of the transformation of the times. Organizations always change because there is no eternal world, everything changes, including the organization; what doesn't change is transformation itself.

Winardi also explained that organizational transformation is an act of switching an organization from the current conditions, to the desired future conditions to increase its effectiveness. In the process of transformation there are forces that help to make the transformation process work, namely competitive forces, economic and political forces, global forces, demographic and social forces and ethical forces. In addition to the strengths which become the blocking forces namely: organizational constraints of power and conflict, differences in functional orientation of mechanistic structures, organizational culture, group constraints, group norms, group socialism, group thought and escalation of commitment, constraints individual constraints, uncertainty and insecurity, selective perception and habit retention.

A number of suggestions for managers, regarding the supporting forces and forces that prevent change are: carrying out periodic analyzes of the organizational environment, and identifying the forces that support the transformation process, conducting analyzes of how transformations in reactions to these forces will affect the people, functions, and divisions within the organization concerned, and finally by utilizing the results of the analysis, deciding what type of transformation will be applied, and then developing a plan to overcome the challenges that arise with the transformation and strengthen the forces that support the transformation.

2.4. Transformation Model in Organizations

Kurt Lewin in Stephen P. Robbins argues that successful transformation in organizations should follow the three steps of unfreezing the status quo, moving to a new state, and refreezing (transforming new transformations to make them permanent). Lewin organization:

Figure Lewin Three-Step Transformation Model

Based on the picture above, it can be more detailed that in the first phase "melting" is the stage where people prepare a situation for transformation. The next stage, the "movement" includes acts of actual modification in humans, tasks, structures and or technology. The final phase, "re-freezing", is the final stage of the transformation process. It is designed to maintain the momentum of a transformation, where it is positively "frozen" the desired results. The three types of phases above are more detailed in the figure below:

Figure of Lewin's Three-Step Transformation Model Details

Tyagi in Ismail Nawawi Uha explained Tyagi in Ismail Nawawi Uha explained that Lwin's transformation model was not yet complete, because it did not involve several important issues. The process of transformation is not only concerned with human resource behavior. A systems approach to transformation will provide an overall picture in organizational transformation. The Tyagi model process can be seen in the image below:

However, the most difficult challenge now is how organizations can reduce the risk of resistance to transformation. Thus, a key factor in the success of organizational transformation lies in how organizations anticipate and minimize the risk of resistance to organizational transformation.

The picture below illustrates the flow of thought to arise resistance to organizational transformation as follows: n that Lwin's transformation model is not yet complete, because it does not involve several important issues. The process of transformation is not only concerned with human resource behavior. A systems approach to transformation will provide an overall picture in organizational transformation. The Tyagi model process can be seen in the image below:

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Image of Organizational Transformation Resistance

Kartini Kartono also explained that several important issues that needed to be considered in the transformation process that could provide facilities for the ease of the transformation were as follows:

First the transformation takes time. The time factor is quite important, because transformation in a wide scale or even radical transformation is impossible to take place suddenly in a very short time. Many internal and external difficulties that must be faced by the company are also caused by the limited facilities and organizational structure, as well as the possibilities / prospects for the

future. A company cannot copy the transformation of other companies, because every company / firm has unique characteristics, there are physical conditions that are characteristic, also its employees have unique characteristics and habits. To change the whole thing, it takes a long time.

Both of these organizational structures are unique. The traditions and attitudes of company managers influence the attitudes of employees to emphasize traditional issues. It will be more striking if it has been going on for a long time, from one generation to another; so that there is a traditional joint experience. And in the end foster a special attitude to employees, workers and managers.

Third, the balance between costs and profits. To make a drastic transformation, it is necessary to pay close attention to the balance between the costs incurred and the expected benefits. For the sake of the company's sustainability, it is necessary to pay attention to the various internal and external factors that affect the transformation process, as well as the urgency of transformation.

Fourth effective communication. If people don't understand the motivation for transformation in an organization or company, they certainly don't want to change their attitude. People must realize the need for transformation, and what benefits will be gained by introducing transformation for this to require effective communication, for the smooth delivery of information. The motivation must be clear, namely the motivation for attitude transformation and the motivation for company overhaul or reorganization. The support of these employees cannot be obtained by force or command; but can only be obtained by way of awareness.

The fifth anxiety about things that are not yet known need to be controlled. New organizations, new ways, new tools and machines, new management and attitudes all cause doubt and anxiety. There is a feeling of insecurity and disbelief in one's own abilities. Therefore, all doubts and anxieties need to be controlled, then eliminated. So that the trust and rationality arise regarding the truth of the transformation activities, in accordance with the wishes of the leader. Sources of anxiety must be removed, so as not to cause confusion and inferior feelings. The effectiveness of management in introducing new systems and methods needs to be enhanced, so that with confidence, employees can learn new skills and methods.

The six active participation of executive executives. Even though important decisions are determined by the leader / employer / highest management, namely by the president, director, but all transformation plans and their implementation (implementation), could not have been carried out without the assistance and active participation of executive executives in key positions. It is they who must especially have the most responsibility for the successful operations of the transformation.

Seventh strengthening process (enforcement). Because the attitudes and behavior of many adults have a lot of "grilling" and are relatively fixed, making getting used to patterns and habits is not as easy as people think. The customization of the new pattern needs to be accompanied by a regular and relatively continuous control system. This new patterning habit needs to be accompanied by an orderly and disciplined control system. If necessary, general policies regarding employment, labor selection, the assignment and placement system, promotion and compensation systems must

all be changed, for the sake of company efficiency. As well as being able to stimulate all employees to make adaptations to the transformation patterns that are being carried out.

Eighth continuous progress. Slow or fast, the transformation will take place continuously and continuously; both intentional and unintentional and well planned, needs to be sustained for the sake of high efficiency. The process of transformation will never end (unless the company has already gone bankrupt, bankrupt), in the form of shifts and transfers at certain times with different intensities. A calm period can be followed by an active period full of dynamics and radical overhaul, to respond to the demands of the times and new needs. Various revision, reconstruction, and reorganization efforts need to be carried out continuously, so that the company becomes flexible and effective in overcoming any difficulties that arise in a row.

3. Conclusions

Transformation can cover everything in the organization. Transformation targets include the transformation of organizational structure, technology, physical regulation, human resources, work mechanism processes, and culture in an organization. Transformation in organizations is caused by environmental factors, both external and internal environments.

Transformation in educational organizations is closely related to New demand: educational accountability. Competency standards and measurements to assess student achievement. If you agree with this, in Indonesia, the demand for accountability triggers transformation in the education system. The National Final Examination, standardization, accreditation, is the response of the Indonesian education world to the demands of education accountability.

Transformation can also occur due to redesigning the organization for production feasibility. Other causes of transformation in organizations are conflicts, willingness of internal resources, or change of leadership. Transformation targets include the transformation of organizational structure, technology, physical regulation, human resources, work mechanism processes, and culture in an organization.

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